

"The Challenges Encountered By Affiliated Colleges of Periyar University in Establishing NDLI Clubs in Their Institutions -Action Research Approach" (The Study was sponsored by the Indian Council of Social Science Research- New Delhi under Major Research Project – PU-ICSSR-MJRP139)

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Abstract

The NDLI Club is an initiative in the Indian Digital Education platform aimed at revolutionizing the educational landscape. Its primary objective is to engage learners and promote the effective use of the National Digital Library of India's resources through competitions, training sessions, and workshops. However, the reach of the NDLI Club remains limited, with only 2500+ registered clubs in colleges, indicating the need for expansion and awareness. To address this, a study was conducted to identify challenges faced by colleges in establishing NDLI Clubs. Using Kurt Lewin's action research model, teachers were made aware of the NDLI Club and encouraged to initiate clubs in their colleges. Interviews with key members revealed three main challenges: registration, event creation, and report submission. Only five out of 17 colleges fulfilled all registration requirements. Recommendations were proposed to overcome challenges and increase registrations, including organizing awareness programs, providing vernacular-based technical support, and implementing a user-friendly event creation and report submission system. Further research can explore successful implementations, best practices, and the impact of NDLI Clubs on student learning outcomes and teacher professional development.

Keywords: Digital Library, NDLI, NDLI Club, Digital Learning,

Introduction:

The National Digital Library of India Club (NDLI Club) serves as an invaluable platform for individuals who are eager to enhance their educational and professional journeys. It caters to a diverse range of users, including learners, job seekers, researchers, and students, providing them with ample opportunities to further their knowledge, skills, and attributes. NDLI Clubs are established within educational institutions and nodal organizations, acting as hubs of activity aimed at cultivating holistic growth beyond the confines of the standard curriculum. These clubs play a vital role in supporting students' advancement within their respective fields by organizing a variety of events and activities. (Bhowmick et al., 2022)

The NDLI Clubs host a wide array of events that foster the acquisition of knowledge, the development of skills, and the cultivation of personal characteristics that are instrumental for success in specific professional domains. These events can take place either in physical settings or virtually through the NDLI Club platform. Virtual events, conducted online, offer the flexibility of participation from anywhere in the world. They are facilitated by the robust technological infrastructure provided by the NDLI Club platform, ensuring seamless and engaging experiences for participants.

Events organized by NDLI Clubs are strategically planned at various levels, spanning from the institute level to the city, district, state,

region, and even the national level. This multi-tiered approach allows for targeted engagement with learners at different stages of their educational journey and promotes collaboration and networking opportunities within specific geographic areas. By bringing together students, educators, industry experts, and other stakeholders, these events create an enriching environment for learning, sharing ideas, and fostering professional connections.

Access to a wide range of educational resources is crucial for the development of knowledge, skills, and attributes. NDLI Club members benefit from unrestricted access to an extensive collection of free and open learning resources available through the National Digital Library of India (NDLI) website. This access is not limited by geographical constraints, enabling users to tap into the wealth of educational materials at their convenience, regardless of their location. The National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NMEICT), under the purview of the Ministry of Education (MOE), Government of India, oversees the NDLI and NDLI Club initiatives. These efforts are integral components of the broader National Digital India Mission, which aims to harness the power of technology for comprehensive educational transformation.

The NDLI endeavors to cater to the diverse needs of learners by providing educational content in the most commonly spoken Indian languages.

This inclusive approach ensures that individuals at all academic levels, including lifelong learners, have access to relevant and high-quality learning materials across a wide range of subjects. By facilitating comprehensive educational resources and promoting multilingual accessibility, NDLI empowers individuals to study, learn, and prepare for their future endeavors effectively.

Ndli Club Registration Process

The registration process for the NDLI Club involves several important steps to ensure successful participation and access to the resources provided by the National Digital Library of India. Firstly, the institution must identify four key members who will form the core team of the club. These members will play a crucial role in facilitating the club's activities and engagement with the NDLI platform. (NDLI, n.d.) The next step is for the key members to individually register themselves on the official NDLI website. This step establishes their presence as authorized representatives of the institution. Once registered, they proceed to the NDLI Club Registration website to enter the necessary details about their college and the key members. To complete the registration process, a formal letter needs to be generated, incorporating the institution's official letterhead. This letter, along with the required documentation, must be submitted to the designated authorities.

After the submission, the authorities receive a self-verification email, which prompts them to verify their details and ensure their accuracy. Once the self-verification process is completed, the NDLI technical team reviews the provided information and approves the authorities' registration. Upon approval, a unique passkey is generated exclusively for the institution. This passkey serves as a verification mechanism and grants access to the NDLI Club's privileges and resources.

Within 30 days of receiving approval, it becomes mandatory for the institution to register a minimum of 100 club members on the NDLI platform using the unique passkey. This requirement aims to encourage active participation and engagement within the institution's NDLI Club.

Additionally, the institution is expected to organize an Awareness Session under the NDLI Event, which serves to disseminate information and raise awareness about the resources available on the NDLI platform.

Upon fulfilling the registration requirements and successfully conducting the Awareness Session, the institution becomes eligible to generate the NDLI Registration Certificate. This certificate, valid for one year, signifies the institution's official recognition as an active member of the NDLI Club.

Importance and Scope of Ndli Club

The NDLI Club holds immense importance in the future of education as it aligns with the evolving needs of students and the advancements in digital learning. With the ongoing pandemic, there has been a significant shift towards remote and online learning. In this context, the NDLI Club plays a crucial role in providing students with access to a vast array of digital resources and fostering a conducive learning environment.

Jesse Stommel, a prominent figure in the field of digital pedagogy, emphasizes the essential components of effective digital learning (Stommel & Morris, n.d.).

1. Collaboration is one such component, and the NDLI Club actively promotes it among students. By encouraging collaborative learning activities, the club cultivates a sense of community and cooperation, enabling students to learn from each other's perspectives and experiences.
2. Playfulness and tinkering are also key elements of digital pedagogy, and the NDLI Club recognizes their significance. By offering an online platform for learning-oriented activities, the club encourages students to explore, experiment, and engage in hands-on learning experiences. This playful approach stimulates curiosity, creativity, and critical thinking skills, making the learning process more enjoyable and effective.
3. Another crucial aspect emphasized by Stommel is the focus on process and building. The NDLI Club places great emphasis on iterative processes and the construction of knowledge. By participating in the club's activities, students are encouraged to delve into the intricacies of a subject, develop a deeper understanding, and build upon their existing knowledge. This approach not only enhances their core competencies but also nurtures important skills such as problem-solving, analysis, and synthesis.

Furthermore, the NDLI Club offers additional benefits by collaborating with educational institutions. It provides a platform for teachers to assign subject-specific tasks and assignments to students, utilizing the extensive resources available through the NDLI. By completing these assignments, students can earn credible certificates as participants of the NDLI Club. This recognition not only motivates students but also validates their efforts and achievements, increasing their engagement and commitment to the learning process.

Overall, the NDLI Club's scope extends beyond merely providing access to digital resources. It actively promotes collaboration, playfulness, and

a focus on the process of learning. By embracing these principles of digital pedagogy, the club empowers students to become active learners, equipped with essential skills and knowledge for their academic and personal growth

The Research Problem:

The limited visibility and reach of the NDLI Club within the teaching community pose a significant challenge that highlights the necessity and scope for further research in this area. It is evident that many colleges have not yet registered under the NDLI Club, and even among those registered, the level of activity in organizing events and promoting the club remains low. According to a report by Sornamohan in October 2021, the number of institutions actively engaged in the NDLI Club was only around 2500+ (Sornamohan, 2021).

This situation underscores the importance of investigating the reasons behind the low adoption and engagement rates among colleges and the teaching community. A research study can delve deeper into understanding the factors that hinder the widespread implementation of the NDLI Club and identify potential strategies to enhance its visibility and participation. By conducting this research, valuable insights can be gained regarding the perceptions, challenges, and opportunities surrounding the NDLI Club among educators. The study can explore the reasons why colleges have been hesitant to register and actively participate in the club's activities. Factors such as lack of awareness, limited resources, technological barriers, or competing priorities could be potential barriers that need to be addressed.

The limited visibility and engagement of the NDLI Club within the teaching community underscore the need for a research study to

investigate the reasons behind this situation and explore strategies to enhance its reach and impact. Such a study can provide valuable insights, identify barriers and opportunities, and guide efforts to promote the NDLI Club's adoption among colleges and the broader teaching community.

Research Design:

The research conducted for this study was undertaken as a significant project at Periyar University. The target respondents were teachers from affiliated colleges who had previously signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) for the Major Research Project. A total of 17 colleges expressed their interest in participating in the study, making them the focal points of data collection and analysis.

Given that the study aimed to address a real-life problem, the researcher employed the Action Research methodology and specifically adopted the Lewinian Action Research model to guide the study. The Lewinian model, developed by Kurt Lewin, is characterized by a cyclical process of planning, action, and reflection. It typically involves stages such as diagnosing the situation, planning for change, implementing the change, evaluating the outcomes, and reflecting on the entire process. This approach emphasizes collaboration and active participation from all stakeholders involved. (Lewin, n.d.)

To provide a clear understanding of how the researcher applied the Lewinian Action Research model in this study, a table outlining the sequential steps and their corresponding actions was included. The table served as a visual representation of the process and showcased the researcher's adherence to the model throughout the study.

	Lewinian Action Research model	The Study Design
Step-1	Diagnosing the situation	In this stThe Researcher identified the need to train and raise awareness among teachers about NDLI (National Digital Library of India) and establish NDLI clubs in their colleges. This diagnosis stage involves recognizing the problem or challenge you aim to address.
Step-2	Planning	The Researcher planned and conducted training sessions to educate teachers about NDLI and its potential benefits. This planning phase focuses on designing interventions or actions to address the identified challenge
Step-3	Action	Following the training, The Researcher asked the teachers to start NDLI clubs in their colleges. This stage involves implementing the planned actions or interventions.
Step-4	Observation and reflection	During the process, The Researcher observed that many teachers faced different challenges while establishing the NDLI clubs. This stage involves collecting data, observing the outcomes, and reflecting on the experiences and results of the

		implemented actions.
Step-5	Analysis and interpretation	The Researcher studied and analyzed the challenges faced by the teachers in establishing NDLI clubs. This step involves analyzing the data collected, interpreting the findings, and identifying patterns or themes
Step-6	Recommendation and suggestion	Based on the analysis, The Researcher provided recommendations and suggestions to address the challenges faced by the teachers. This stage involves formulating practical suggestions or solutions based on the insights gained from the research.

The research was conducted in two phases and followed an action-based approach.

Phase 1: Creating Awareness

The primary aim of the first phase was to generate awareness about the National Digital Library of India (NDLI) among the teachers from the participating colleges. To achieve this, a webinar titled "National Digital Library: Free E-Learning Resources Repository" was organized. The webinar featured Dr. Vignesh Sornamohan, Chief Strategic and Outreach Officer at NDLI-IITKGP, as the resource person. A total of 159 teachers participated in this highly informative session.

During the webinar, the teachers had the opportunity to experience firsthand the enhanced effectiveness of the NDLI in searching for credible study materials as compared to using general search engines like Google. The session covered several key topics, including an introduction to the NDLI, instructions on how to access the NDLI platform, information on the NDLI mobile app, a comparison between the NDLI and Google, and guidance on operating the NDLI Club. Importantly, the session provided detailed insights on establishing the NDLI Club within their respective colleges.

Based on the findings from this initial phase, it was discovered that out of the 17 participating colleges, only two colleges were already registered as NDLI Club members, and even these colleges demonstrated minimal activity in organizing events under the NDLI Club. This data underscored the urgent need for more awareness programs and campaigns to effectively promote and encourage the adoption of the NDLI Club across various colleges.

Phase 2: Establishing the NDLI Club and Promoting Activities

The second phase of this study aimed to establish the NDLI Club and actively promote its activities among the participating colleges. To commence this phase, the researcher requested the colleges to identify key members who would form the club within their institutions. Subsequently, a

The Registration Process Outcome:

- 17 Colleges** participated in the training workshop session
- 14 Colleges** were able to register NDLI Club
- 8 Colleges** were able to create an event and conduct awareness programme
- 5 Colleges** were successfully uploaded their report and received a "Certificate of Registration"

comprehensive training workshop titled "How to Run and Manage NDLI Club Activities Successfully" was organized for key members of various colleges.

The workshop brought together key members and department representatives from the participating colleges, and it featured Dr. C. Murugan, Professor & Head of the Department of Library and Information Sciences at Periyar University, as the invited expert. During the workshop, various aspects related to the NDLI Club registration process were thoroughly explained. This included step-by-step instructions such as identifying four key members, registering on the NDLI website, providing college and key member details on the NDLI Club Registration website, generating and submitting the required letters, completing the self-verification process, obtaining technical team approval, receiving a unique passkey for the institution, and registering a minimum of 100 club members within 30 days of approval. Additionally, the workshop emphasized the importance of conducting awareness sessions under NDLI events and obtaining the NDLI Registration Certificate, which remains valid for one year.

After the completion of the workshop session, the researcher urged the participating colleges to initiate the NDLI Club Registration process in accordance with the guidelines provided and asked to conduct an event and upload the event report on the NDLI club website and generate the "Certificate of Registration."

Following the workshop program, a 30-day time period was given to the participating institutions to establish the NDLI club in their respective colleges. After this time period, the research conducted an interview process among the key members of the NDLI club from various colleges to identify the challenges faced by them during the NDLI Registration Process.

During the training workshop session, a total of 17 colleges actively participated and engaged in the learning process. The workshop aimed to provide valuable insights and guidance to the participating colleges on effectively utilizing the National Digital Library of India (NDLI) platform.

Out of the 17 colleges, 14 were successful in registering their NDLI Club, which is a commendable achievement. This indicates the enthusiasm and interest shown by these colleges in creating a dedicated space for NDLI-related activities and resources within their institutions.

Moving forward, a significant milestone was reached by 8 colleges that managed to go beyond the registration process and create their own events. These events were aimed at raising awareness among students about the valuable resources available on the NDLI platform. The successful execution of these awareness programs demonstrates the colleges' dedication and effort in promoting digital learning and research initiatives among their student communities. Furthermore, the report submission process was a crucial aspect of the NDLI Club initiative, and it was heartening to see that 5 colleges were able to complete this task successfully. By uploading their reports, these colleges showcased their commitment to documenting their activities and sharing their experiences with the larger NDLI community. The "Certificate of Registration" received by these colleges serves as a recognition of their efforts and adds to their credibility.

The challenges for teachers throughout its various stages includes technical errors encountered during registration, difficulties in the self-verification process, complexities in event creation, limited authority in organizing events, and issues related to report submission.

Challenges Faced By The Teacher:

The passage discusses the challenges faced by teachers in the context of the NDLI Club, based on interviews conducted by researchers with key authorities from different colleges participating in the club. These interviews revealed several issues that teachers encountered throughout the club's processes, ranging from registering the club to uploading event reports. The researchers categorized these challenges into three main areas for better understanding and analysis.

Challenge 1: Registration Process

The first set of challenges pertains to the registration process. During this stage, four institutions faced a technical error where they received an error message stating that the institution already exists. However, the NDLI team promptly resolved this issue by suggesting a change in the institute code as per the prescribed format. This technical problem was thus resolved in a hassle-free

manner. One of the major difficulties faced by teachers was related to the self-verification process, particularly when it came to self-verifying their patron profile. Despite the active involvement of the President, Secretary, and Executive members in maintaining the NDLI Club, the self-verification of the Patron profile remained mandatory. However, many teachers found it challenging to approach the Patron easily, and sometimes the Patron was unwilling to provide their access ID to other key members, causing delays in the registration process. Additionally, some members initially faced login issues, but the NDLI team effectively solved these problems. Overall, the technical team's support during the registration process was highly commendable.

Challenge 2: Event Creation Process

The second set of challenges revolves around the event creation process. The success conversion rate, which indicates the percentage of institutions successfully creating and conducting awareness programs, decreased significantly. Only 8 the institutions managed to create events successfully. This decline was attributed to the complexity and lengthiness of the questions asked during the event creation process. Many staff members struggled to complete the registration process due to the challenging nature of the questions. Participants expressed the need for more hands-on training in the offline "event creation" process to better understand and navigate the complexities. Another critical issue highlighted was that only executive members had the authority to create events, which prevented other department representatives from hosting events. This restriction on event creation may demotivate department representatives from organizing future events, reducing their overall morale.

Challenge 3: Event Report Submission Process

The final set of challenges pertains to the process of submitting the event report. Once the event has been successfully completed, the members of the NDLI club at the college are required to upload the event report on the NDLI Club portal. If the report is not submitted by the club members of the college, students will not receive a participation certificate from the NDLI club, and the concerned college will not receive an event completion certificate. The success conversion rate during this stage further decreased from 54.14% to 35.71%, primarily due to difficulties encountered in the submission of reports. Both teachers and students faced challenges in this phase, including login issues, problems with bulk registration, difficulties in receiving event notifications, and the inability to submit their outputs. Key members of the NDLI Club emphasized the importance of receiving proper

orientation and guidance support in their regional language to effectively overcome these challenges. In summary, the challenges faced by teachers in the NDLI Club spanned various stages, including registration, event creation, and post-event processes. These challenges encompassed technical errors, difficulties in self-verification, complexity in event creation, limited event creation authority, and issues in report submission. The passage highlights the need for improved support, training, and guidance to address these challenges and ensure a smoother experience for teachers and students participating in the NDLI Club.

Our Recommendations and Suggestions

1. **Organize Awareness Programs and Workshops:** Researchers recommend conducting more awareness programs and workshops at the micro level in various colleges to increase the number of successfully created NDLI Clubs. These programs will help familiarize teachers and students with the club's benefits and processes.
2. **Limit the Role of the Patron:** Since Patrons typically have limited involvement in club activities, researchers suggest delegating operational roles and rights to the President of the club. The Patron's role should be primarily focused on monitoring and overseeing the NDLI Club in their respective institution.
3. **Vernacular-based Technical Support:** Currently, the NDLI technical support team only provides support in English or Hindi. To cater to institutions in Tier-2 and Tier-3 cities across India, researchers propose creating vernacular-based technical teams. This will enable effective problem-solving in local languages.
4. **Remote Desktop Support:** NDLI can promote "Remote Desktop" support for key members facing difficulties in event creation and report submission. By providing video call grievance support, NDLI can remotely access and assist key members in resolving technical issues quickly and efficiently.
5. **Establish Regional Offices:** As the number of NDLI Clubs increases, researchers recommend restructuring the technical support system. NDLI can establish regional offices in different parts of India, similar to NPTEL and SWAYAM, to address issues and promote local chapters effectively.
6. **Hard Copy Registration Process:** Recognizing the limitations in internet connectivity and computer competency in certain areas of India, researchers encourage NDLI to promote a hard copy registration process for club registration. This will ensure inclusivity and enable teachers to participate despite the challenges they may face with technology.

7. **Expand Event Creation Rights:** Currently, only executive members have the authority to create events, limiting other department representatives from hosting events. To foster active engagement, researchers suggest adding an option on the NDLI website that allows both students and teachers to create events. The role of key members can be limited to event approval rather than event creation, encouraging greater participation.
8. **Assignments and Authenticated Certificates:** Various departments in colleges can utilize NDLI Club activities to provide assignments to students, fostering their active involvement. NDLI can facilitate the authentication process and issue certificates upon completion of these assignments, motivating students to actively participate in club activities.
9. **User-Friendly Event Creation and Report Submission:** The researchers recommend that the NDLI team develop the event creation and report submission processes in a simple and user-friendly manner. This will facilitate smoother navigation and encourage more teachers and students to participate in these activities.

Future Scope of Study

The future research study will examine successful cases where institutions will have effectively implemented the NDLI Club and will identify best practices that can be shared with other colleges. Understanding the experiences and perspectives of colleges that will have successfully embraced the club will provide valuable lessons and guidance for promoting wider adoption. Additionally, the future research study will explore the potential benefits and impact of the NDLI Club on student learning outcomes, teacher professional development, and overall educational practices. By examining the outcomes and experiences of those institutions that will be actively engaged in the club, researchers can provide evidence-based insights into the effectiveness and value of the NDLI Club as a digital learning platform.

Conclusion

Implementing these recommendations will benefit all stakeholders involved in the NDLI Club initiative. Teachers will have access to a valuable digital learning platform, students will benefit from enhanced educational resources and engaging activities, and colleges will be able to leverage the NDLI Club for institutional ranking and recognition. Ultimately, the successful implementation of these recommendations will contribute to the broader goal of transforming education through digital platforms and fostering a culture of lifelong learning.

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